

COMMUNICATION WITH A BOOK IS THE HIGHEST AND UNIQUE FORM OF PERSONAL MENTAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *In this article, comments are made about the current tasks aimed at increasing the book reading and reading culture, which is an important basis for the development of the young generation as a perfect person.*

Keywords: *book, reading culture, Internet network, electronic library.*

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 12, 2017 "On the establishment of a commission on the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increasing and promoting book reading and reading culture" is currently awaiting a decision. solving a number of problems, publishing and distributing high-quality books, which are considered an important tool for young people to grow up with high spirituality, and promotion of reading to a new level. responsibility. Developing new methods for teaching students to read and understand books and using them effectively, organizing seminars and trainings promoting reading, organizing meetings with writers and poets, holding book weeks, and includes discussion of rare works of representatives of Uzbek and world literature read by students. Also, in this order, it is necessary to provide readers with fine works, to distribute published books and book products to libraries, bookstores in remote areas and A.R.M important tasks have been defined in connection with the delivery of books at low prices, wide promotion of reading among the population. The president is creating all the conditions, conveniences and opportunities for readers in our country. As one of these opportunities, it is worth mentioning the establishment of new modern libraries, the filling of existing libraries with rare books of world and Uzbek literature, and the launch of electronic libraries. This is the key to unique opportunities for the future prospects of the spiritually strong, deep-minded Uzbek youth.

Today, a number of modern methods are used by pedagogues at various stages of education in order to increase the interest of young people in reading books. As an example, in every literature lesson, students describe the characters of the works read by the students, and they also list the qualities of such heroes that they also have. This shows that the reader can not only evaluate the hero of the work, but also reveal his own good and bad feelings. Through such fair comparisons, first of all, the student's artistic thinking, range of thinking expands and speech develops, and most importantly, the qualities of free thinking and expressing one's opinion in front of others are formed in the student. It is not for nothing that the great Russian writer M. Gorky said, "I am grateful to the book for all the good feelings I have." Actually, in the process of reading a book and reading it, only and only good feelings are formed in the personality of the reader. In fact, the person who reads the book does not allow his conscience and spirituality to do bad things. Therefore, reading books leads young people to perfection and saves them from ignorance. In today's society, where science and technology, information and communication, the Internet and several modern mobile communication programs are developed, it seems like a difficult task to return and interest young people to reading books. But it will give its effective result only if the

teacher, father - mother, community - seriously approach this task. At this point, I considered it appropriate to quote the following thoughts of the national poet of Uzbekistan, Sirojiddin Sayyid: "Farhad and Shirin" from "Khamasa" of our grandfather Navoi, who can bend the horn and cut the vein, in the age of computers, in the age of the Internet, while reading his epic, I seemed to discover an interesting miracle that was unexpected for me:

The age of the Internet is wonderful.
Say it from the ancient magic of the Far East:
Farhad saw Shirin for the first time.
From Hazrat Navoi's computer.

Also, our honorable President Sh. Mirziyoyev also emphasizes such thoughts: Today's children will become the people of tomorrow. We need to return young people to books. Along with mastering the latest achievements in the field of information and communication, it is necessary to pay special attention to increasing the interest of young people in reading books, making them friends with books, and increasing the reading level of the population. Development and high spirituality cannot be achieved without books. Neither a person nor a nation has a future who does not read books. In fact, these ideas have already been confirmed, and here, first of all, the interest of young people in reading books is formed from the family. A person who is born and formed in a family, only if he reads books, will become a person who thinks freely, does not give in to any negative influences, evaluates the events around him truthfully, puts the interests of the society, the state, and the people above his own, and becomes an initiative person. For example, if a parent in a family or a teacher in a school insists on preparing a lesson, if he makes them interested in reading, the child will certainly understand it. In it, the ability to fulfill one's obligation and duty will be born. From a young age, he seeks to do something. The family environment has a great influence on the child's education. By instilling love for fiction in children from a young age, skills such as enjoying life, distinguishing between good and bad, striving for goodness, acting with judgment, self-restraint in any situation, and having an independent opinion are formed.

Bibliography as a science is "a book as an objective phenomenon of social existence, such as: systematized scientific knowledge about the nature and essence of a book, its existence, movement, development, and logical and historical forms, processes, and laws; method of acquiring new knowledge about the book: organizing the results of knowledge of the book into theoretical components and elements of knowledge in the field of book studies (categories, concepts, definitions, observations, concepts, concepts, theories), or theoretically developed rules, methods, methods method - i.e., the methods of book studies (book publishing, book sales, librarianship, bibliography) in one or another aspect of bookkeeping". The status of general bibliography as a special scientific methodology determines the range of such theoretical issues, the solution of which constitutes the content of this relatively independent sub-system of bibliographic knowledge:

- to determine and study the essence and the most general logical and historical laws of the book as an objective phenomenon of social existence, as well as the emergence, development and methods of existence (that is, processes and forms) of the book as a method of existence of the book. ;

- researching the historical process of bibliographic knowledge and the laws of its emergence and development;

- substantiating the object, subject, structure, interdisciplinary and intra-disciplinary relations of book studies knowledge;
- development and coherent statement of the theory of the method of bibliographic knowledge:
 - development and systematization of the apparatus of categories and concepts of bibliography;
 - development of book typology as a methodological basis for typology and classification of book publications in special book studies and some disciplines;
 - general principles of scientific knowledge in book studies: objectivity, reflection and development, systematicity, unity of theory and practice, as well as interpretation of historical and logical approach;
 - to study the nature and forms of interactions between book studies and other scientific disciplines;
 - development of the scientific basis of management of the practice of book publishing and the processes of the book's use in society. The listed problems represent the system of the subject of general bibliography more fully. In general, it can be described as a comprehensive and consistent statement of the general theory of the book and the general theory of scientific knowledge about it.

The object of general bibliography is the theoretical model of the multi-level system "book in book work". Prof. A. A. Belovitskaya, while analyzing the field of objects of the science of book and library work, writes: "... the object of specialized book studies includes the corresponding type of practical activity in the field of book studies - book publishing, book sales, librarianship, the model of bibliography activity is introduced, because in the field of book forms and some of its scientific objects, at the level of existence method forms, a real book in the form of a book publication and its existence forms apply. The activity of practical bibliography is aimed at its creation, bibliography, distribution, distribution and redistribution with the tools of book trade and librarianship. The theory and system of the typological method or typification method developed in the methodology of bibliography is of great importance from the point of view of its application to book history and the phenomena of book publishing. The typological method or typological method is "a multi-stage method of scientific thinking that uses the main methods of thinking (abstraction, indirect expression, generalization) in order to accurately reflect the phenomenon under study." Typological method of bibliography in accordance with the general, special and certain levels of organization of the object and similar levels of knowledge organization, bibliography typological) method exists in the dialectic unity of some science typological (historical-book publishing studies, historical bibliopolistic typological, historical-library studies typological. Historical bibliography typological) methods. However, the typological method of bibliography is not limited by this hierarchy of existence levels, its system and knowledge possibilities. The typological method itself typifies the knowledge that the researcher aims to obtain in accordance with the set goal in each of the above-mentioned levels of existence. The typological method is a dialectical unity of the general forms of its existence, such as the historical-typological method of bibliography and the logical-typological method. Their similarities and differences reflect the dialectic of history and logic in scientific knowledge. Its essence is expressed in the principle of the unity of historicity and logic: "The historical approach is not only a reflection of the phenomenon under study, but also the laws that determine the transition from

one stage of the formation and development of the object to another. It also implies the identification of important connections between; therefore, historicity in the dialectical method does not exclude rationality, but is in harmony with it. Here, historicity is free from coincidences, corrected according to the law of the historical process. It is a form of logical movement that reflects the important connections and relationships that are manifested in the process of formation and development of the object being studied. Historical-typological and logical typological subsystems of the typological method, in turn, can appear in the form of their types depending on the consistency of the typological process: "component-typological method, functional-typological method. Each of them applies in its historical aspect, with the historical formation and development of the structure, structure and functions of the phenomenon of bibliography studied and explained, the essence, method and forms of existence of the phenomenon of bibliography, its composition if the theory of its structure and functions is developed and explained, it is valid in its logical aspect. Historical and logical aspects of the typological method are usually used in parallel in any specific and integrated bibliographic research...».

In conclusion, our Motherland itself is a great and iconic book. To read and understand this glorious book, to reach its value and value, to honor it by being a true and loyal, enlightened and educated child is a lot, a lot, a lot. Every boy and girl who realizes the necessity and necessity of reading beautiful books can become the most handsome and happy lover of this country, and in his heart, who keeps constant companionship with the book, he will get rid of destructive ideas no remains.

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